

Coverage and quality of open metadata for Dutch research output

ORIA Pilot

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Table of contents

[0. Executive summary](#)

[1. Introduction](#)

[Alignment with values and principles](#)

[Reasons for using open research information](#)

[Landscape sketch](#)

[Scope](#)

[2. Methodology](#)

[Source data](#)

[Dutch research organisations](#)

[Coverage of research output](#)

[Coverage of metadata types](#)

[4. Coverage comparison of research output](#)

[Total research output](#)

[Overlap between databases](#)

[Discussion & Conclusions](#)

[5. Data flows](#)

[OpenAlex](#)

[OpenAIRE](#)

[6. Recommendations](#)

[7. References](#)

[8. Data availability](#)

[Appendices](#)

[Appendix 1](#)

[Appendix 2](#)

[Appendix 3](#)

0. Executive summary

To guarantee both digital sovereignty and quality in reporting, evaluation and findability of Dutch research, Universities of the Netherlands (UNL) recognizes that research information (i.e. metadata on research activities, outputs and impacts, including information on research performing organisations and research funders) should be openly available and governed and controlled by the academic community.

Within the Open Research Information Agenda (ORIA), open metadata can play a role in several ways: as primary source for persistent identifiers (PIDs) and accompanying metadata for research output, both for direct filling of CRIS systems as for national systems such as UKBSis and a national PID graph, and as secondary source for enrichment of existing records (from CRIS systems), by adding missing PIDs and metadata.

This pilot investigates the potential of both 'tracks' by mapping existing data flows between sources of open metadata, comparing the coverage of Dutch research output in open data sources, and, for research output available in multiple systems: the coverage and quality of available metadata (including PIDs).

Coverage comparison of research output

The pilot explores OpenAlex and OpenAIRE as sources of open research information, focussing on research output of Dutch universities and university medical centres. Results for other groups of Dutch research performing organisations (NWO institutes, KNAW institutes and Universities of Applied Sciences) are added to give an indication of their coverage in OpenAlex and OpenAIRE and compare it to that of universities and university medical centres.

For identifying research output from Dutch research performing organisations based on ROR IDs, OpenAlex and OpenAIRE currently are complementary resources, with only partial overlap in records that are assigned to Dutch research performing organisations. For publication year 2022, OpenAlex almost exclusively returns research output with Crossref DOIs, while OpenAIRE also contains a considerable proportion of records without DOI that are identified as affiliated with Dutch RPOs, as well as records with non-Crossref DOIs.

For many publication types with Crossref DOIs, including journal articles, book chapters, preprints and peer reviews, more unique records are retrieved from OpenAlex than from OpenAIRE, although OpenAIRE also has unique records for all these publication types. Among records with Crossref DOIs, dissertations are retrieved exclusively from OpenAIRE,

While for most universities and at least some university medical centres, as well as for many NWO-i institutes, coverage in OpenAIRE (in total number of records) matches or exceeds that in OpenAlex, most KNAW institutes seem less well represented in OpenAIRE than in OpenAlex. Universities of Applied Sciences differ greatly in the amount of research output they produce. Where they do produce research output, this is usually found in both

OpenAlex and OpenAIRE, with, in most cases, more unique records identified in OpenAlex than in OpenAIRE.

In comparing coverage and retrieval of Dutch research performing organisations in OpenAlex and OpenAIRE, both the different coverage, as well as potential differences in the identification of affiliated institutions are observed. While for retrieval purposes, the effect is the same, the potential ways for improvement are very different. In the first case, a database would need to expand its coverage, in the second case, it would need to improve correct identification of affiliated organisations (and matching to organisation identifiers).

Data flows

OpenAlex and OpenAIRE both aggregate metadata from various sources, perform steps to clean, combine, consolidate and enrich this information, and then make the resulting dataset available as open research information through their various interfaces (web interface, API, and/or data snapshots). Understanding how information on Dutch research outputs is collected and enriched by both databases can help assess where possible 'loops' exist in data flows (e.g. where information flows from institutional information systems to aggregators, which are then used again to enrich institutional information systems), where information can best be enriched and by whom, and where existing 'gaps' are in open metadata.

This report provides a narrative description of data flows in OpenAlex and OpenAIRE as a basis for future empirical analysis of data flows of Dutch research outputs into these two databases from various data sources, including CRIS systems,

Recommendations

Considering the availability of metadata for Dutch research output in open data sources, a number of recommendations are made for research organisations, funders and central organisations as UKB and UNL. These recommendations centre around the opportunity open metadata sources provide to transition away from closed information sources, the way open metadata sources are complementary in record coverage and metadata coverage, and the central role of persistent identifiers to facilitate retrieval, matching and enrichment of records. Finally, recommendations are made on how institutions can improve coverage of 'their' research output in open metadata sources, increasing value for everyone

1. Introduction

To guarantee both digital sovereignty and quality in reporting, evaluation and findability of Dutch research, UNL recognizes that research information (i.e. metadata on research activities, outputs and impacts, including information on research performing organisations (RPOs) and research funders) should be openly available and governed and controlled by the academic community. In 2022, a report exploring the scope of the Open Research Information Agenda (UNL 2022) confirmed consensus on the need for open research information, and recommended an iterative approach to further determine whether there is added value for a central 'knowledge base or knowledge graph' or other central services and how improvements can be achieved from local and international sources, using as many open data sources as possible. The Open Science Agenda UNL (UNL, 2023) outlines three strands of work regarding (open) infrastructures for research information that UNL is investing in: UKBSis as datahub for 'reliable and complete information on Dutch publications', the Netherlands Research Portal in OpenAIRE as replacement for NARCIS as national portal, and pilots to further the Open Research Information Agenda.

Alignment with values and principles

The Open Science Agenda UNL, using an adaptation of the Center for Open Science's 'Strategy for Culture Change' (Nosek, 2019), considers open research infrastructures and open research information as a condition to make open science possible. It also highlights digital sovereignty (defined in as 'universities' and academics' ability to take autonomous decisions and actions regarding digital infrastructures and data) as an important principle to safeguard the academic values of scientific progress, individual academic freedom and institutional autonomy (IvIR, 2023). In the context of open research infrastructure and open research information, it is made explicit that control about scientific knowledge, publications, data, metadata, as well as software/algorithms to collect, aggregate and analyse them should remain with scientists and scientific institutions, although collaboration with non-scientific partners is not excluded.

There is also close alignment with the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (UNESCO, 2021), which considers open science infrastructures (including knowledge-based resources such as current research information systems, and open bibliometrics and scientometrics systems for assessing and analysing scientific domains) as one of the four key pillars of open science, as they are needed to support open science and serve the needs of different communities. The UNESCO recommendation states that open science infrastructures should be organised and financed upon an essentially not-for-profit and long-term vision, to guarantee permanent and unrestricted access. In this recommendation, it also points to the community-building efforts that have gone into many open science infrastructures and which are crucial to their long term sustainability.

In the Netherlands specifically, awareness of the issue of open research information (and the research infrastructures involved) increased in 2019-2020 following the 'big deal' negotiations with Elsevier, which in 2019 resulted in a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)

between Elsevier, The Association of Universities in the Netherlands (VSNU, now UNL), the Netherlands Federation of University Medical Centres (NFU) and the Dutch Research Council (NWO) that uniquely combined reading and publishing rights with pilots for the development of new services around research information (NWO, 2019). The MoU included basic principles for such pilots designed together with Elsevier. Acknowledging concerns in the community, following these negotiation outcomes a taskforce solely representing public parties was established to address issues around the responsible use of research information and the role of commercial third party providers in particular. The work of the taskforce resulted in Seven Guiding Principles for Open Research Information (Bijsterbosch et al., 2022), addressing trusted and transparent provenance, openness of metadata, openness of algorithms, enduring access and availability, open standards and interoperability, open collaboration with third parties, and academic sovereignty through governance. A preliminary version of these principles was taken into account in concluding the 2020-2024 Elsevier contract (Elsevier and SURFMarket, 2020), which has since resulted in collaboration between Elsevier and Dutch research organisations around (a.o.) provision and enrichment of metadata around funder information, research data, preprints and author contributions (Elsevier, 2022).

Reasons for using open research information

Within the context outlined above, there are multiple reasons why it's important to both ensure that Dutch research information is made openly available, and that open research information is used for purposes of discovery, research assessment and strategic decision making processes, either by using external databases directly, or when ingesting information to fill or enrich institutional or national information systems (such as CRIS systems or a national data warehouse like UKBSis, PID graph or Open Knowledge Base). First, the use of open metadata ultimately makes the open sharing of information easier, because there are no restrictive licences that prevent sharing and reuse. Secondly, the dependence on commercial providers of metadata is reduced when open data sources are also used for source data. Thirdly, research institutions and funders can stimulate the availability and quality of open metadata by choosing to support open metadata providers (also financially) and by including the availability of open metadata in negotiations with publishers. The scope and urgency for this will be greater when institutions actually commit to the use of open metadata.

Landscape sketch

Research information at research performing institutions

Research information is currently available at institutions via the institution's current research information system (CRIS) and via external databases, both closed sources (e.g. Scopus, Web of Science, Dimensions) and open sources. CRIS are managed by institutions themselves and are filled with information provided by researchers, supplemented with information from closed and open systems (see below). Most (but not all) universities and

university medical centres (UMCs) in the Netherlands, and also all KNAW institutes, use Pure (Elsevier) as CRIS (and sometimes also as a repository, see below).

Three relevant pilots are currently running with Elsevier to enrich research information in CRIS. This concerns datasets, funding information and preprints respectively (Elsevier, 2022). Institutions can import this enriched information into their CRIS system (not limited to Pure) and also make it openly available if desired. In the Netherlands, UKBSis is also maintaining and further developing a database with information about publications within publishing deals. The starting point for this data is information provided by publishers, enriched with information from external closed and open sources (including Scopus and formerly NARCIS). Within UKBSis, an exploration is underway with OA Switchboard to enrich publisher data with authorised data from funders and institutions.

Finally, institutions also manage institutional repositories, whose metadata are available via the OAI-PMH protocol. Information from repositories and select information from CRIS systems is currently also being made available to OAI-PMH harvesters (such as BASE and OpenAIRE).

Funding information

Information about research output linked to funding is collected by some (international) funders in their own information system, usually based on reporting by researchers. Some funders also make this information publicly available, either as a dataset (FWF), or via an API on their information system (UKRI). In the Netherlands, NWO provides data on research projects through their website and directly to OpenAIRE, and recently launched a public API through which information on projects can be retrieved together with information on research outputs resulting from projects, based on researcher reporting (NWO, 2023). Publication output is also shared as a dataset in the context of yearly open access monitoring (Waltman and Lamers, 2022, de Jonge, Sondervan and Carbo, 2023). These reports use data from Dimensions and Crossref, respectively.

Open research information

Open research information is currently publicly available from several types of sources, including PID registrations with associated metadata, metadata aggregators (either as database or as research graph), and information systems managed by institutions and funders.

- **PID registrations with associated metadata**
 - [Crossref](#), [DataCite](#) - PIDs and metadata for research output
 - [ORCID](#) - PIDs for researchers, link with research output
 - [ROR](#) - PIDs for research institutions
 - [Open Funder Registry](#) - PIDs for funders¹
 - [GrantID](#) - PID for grants

¹ Crossref recently announced the intention to switch from the Open Funder Registry to ROR for funder IDs (French et al., 2023)

- **Metadata aggregators / Research graphs**
 - [OpenCitations](#), [OpenCitations Meta](#) - PIDs and metadata for citations, including from Crossref and DataCite
 - [Bielefeld Academic Search Engine \(BASE\)](#), [CORE](#) - metadata for repository items (for the Netherlands via NARCIS (until summer 2023) and individual repositories)
 - [OpenAlex](#), [OpenAIRE](#) - research graphs/PID graphs with links between research output, researchers, institutions and funders (using PIDs where possible)

- **Institutional/funder information systems and repositories**
 - As described above; information (in whole or in part) available via OAI-PMH, APIs or published datasets

It is important to emphasise that open research information (open metadata) is already being used by institutions, publishers, and funders to enrich data within their own organisations, and that providers of closed data sources also use open metadata (including PIDs), in addition to data that they obtain/enrich themselves, for example based on full-text research output and data directly from publishers.

As apparent from this landscape sketch, there are dependencies and data flows between different sources of open research information. On one hand, this underscores the added value of open metadata (the possibility of reuse and enrichment). On the other hand it raises questions about where possible 'loops' exist in data flows (e.g. where information flows from institutional information systems to aggregators, which are then used again to enrich institutional information systems), where information can best be enriched and by whom, and where 'gaps' are in open metadata.

Scope

Within the Open Research Information Agenda, open metadata can play a role in two ways: as primary source for PIDs and accompanying metadata for research output, both for direct filling of CRIS systems as for national systems such as UKBSis and a national PID graph, and as secondary source for enrichment of existing records (from CRIS systems), by adding missing PIDs and metadata.

This pilot investigates the potential of both 'tracks' by mapping existing data flows between sources of open metadata, comparing the coverage of Dutch research output in open data sources, and, for research output available in multiple systems: the coverage and quality of available metadata (including PIDs).

Selected open data sources

This pilot explores OpenAlex and OpenAIRE as sources of open research information. Both are research graphs with links between research output, researchers, institutions and (for OpenAIRE) funders, using PIDs as much as possible.

OpenAlex and OpenAIRE differ in method, coverage and available metadata. It therefore is useful to include both sources in a comparison, in order to be able to make a well-founded judgement about (added) value for collecting and using Dutch research information.

OpenAlex

There is growing interest among research performing institutions, including Dutch institutions, in the potential of [OpenAlex](#) as a source for open research information. OpenAlex uses various PIDs (DOIs, ROR, ORCID, Wikidata for disciplines) to enrich and link records. OpenAlex's coverage includes all research output registered in Crossref as well as research output without DOIs, obtained through own harvesting and former harvesting by Microsoft Academic. In the near future, DataCite will also be included in OpenAlex, which is important for the coverage of datasets, among other types of outputs. OpenAlex also started to include funding information, currently only from Crossref. OpenAlex currently contains over 245M research objects. OpenAlex data is available via API and as data dump in JSON format (update frequency: monthly). The data is available under a CC0 licence.

OpenAIRE

[OpenAIRE](#) collects information from various data sources, including institutional repositories, CRIS systems, and directly from journals (via Crossref). The OpenAIRE Research Graph links research output to project funding, with information on projects collected directly from a limited number of funders, especially for EC projects. Coverage for other funders is limited. OpenAIRE currently contains over 174M research objects. OpenAIRE data is available via API and as data dump in JSON format (update frequency: semi-annually). The data is available under a CC-BY licence.

In July 2023, the [Netherlands Research Portal](#) was launched as a national portal for Dutch research output - the result of a collaboration between UKB, SURF and OpenAIRE (Aritzi, 2023). The Netherlands Research Portal is a subset of the OpenAIRE research graph, and to ensure maximal coverage, Dutch research institutions are encouraged to ensure OpenAIRE can harvest their repositories and CRIS systems.

Metadata types

For the purpose of this analysis, all research outputs in OpenAlex and OpenAIRE are in scope, although the majority of output in both databases currently consists of textual output, in particular journal articles. Table 1 in the Methodology section shows the publication types distinguished in both databases.

For all research outputs, information will be collected on a set of metadata elements, including PIDs where available. The focus will be on the following metadata types and PIDs:

- research output (DOIs)²
- contributors (ORCID)
- organisations (ROR)
- funding (Funder ID)³

² Both OpenAlex and OpenAIRE also contain PubMed identifiers (PMIDs) and PubMed Central identifiers (PMcIDs), in addition, OpenAIRE also includes handles and arXiv IDs and, for datasets and software, also Uniprot, ENA, PDB and W3C identifiers.

³ Both OpenAlex and OpenAIRE also contain information on individual grants

2. Methodology

Source data

OpenAlex and OpenAIRE data are available as JSON objects and can be queried and analysed in various ways. For this pilot, [Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative \(COKI\)](#) infrastructure is used, where a number of open data sources (including Crossref, OpenAlex and OpenAIRE) are ingested into a Google Big Query environment, and can then be queried via SQL.

Crossref

Crossref provides monthly snapshots of their metadata corpus to Metadata Plus⁴ subscribers. The dataset, available in XML and JSON format, consists of all Crossref DOIs with complete associated metadata. This analysis uses the Metadata Plus data snapshot release from August 31, 2023.

OpenAlex

OpenAlex provides monthly snapshots of their database which can be downloaded from Amazon S3⁵. The snapshot, provided in JSON line format, consists of seven tables (each split into smaller files for easier handling), with one table for each of OpenAlex entity types:

- Authors
- Concepts
- Funders
- Institutions
- Publishers
- Sources
- Works

The file for each entity consists of a table of that entity's records, each with an entity-specific ID and associated metadata. Metadata for Works include IDs for associated other entities (like Authors, Institutions and Funders), which can be used to match to the other entity tables (see Figure 1).

This analysis uses the OpenAlex data snapshot release from December 20, 2023, which is the latest date entries in the dataset were created or updated.

⁴ <https://www.crossref.org/services/metadata-retrieval/metadata-plus/>

⁵ <https://openalex.s3.amazonaws.com/browse.html>

Table

Figure 1 - Schematic representation of dataset organisation of OpenAlex

OpenAIRE

OpenAIRE provides snapshots of their research graph approximately every six months via Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/openaire>). Each snapshot, provided in JSON line format, consists of a set of tables (each split into smaller files for easier handling), with one table for each of OpenAIRE's entity types. There are four entity types for research outputs:

- Publication
- Dataset
- Software
- Other Research Product

And three other entity types:

- Organisation
- Project
- Datasource

The file for each entity consists of a table of that entity's records, each with an entity-specific ID and associated metadata. A separate Relation table contains information about the relations between different entity IDs, together with the type of relation. This can be used to match the various entity tables together (see Figure 2)..

Finally, the data snapshot contains an additional table 'Community Infrastructures' with metadata records about research communities and research infrastructures. These represent the research community with separate collections in the OpenAIRE research graph (like the Netherlands Research Portal and can be used to identify records of other entity types to these communities.

This analysis uses v.7.0.0 of the OpenAIRE data snapshot release, from January 16, 2024 (Manghi et al. 2023), with the accompanying schema description (Baglioni, M et al.. (2023)). The latest date of collection of entries in this database was December 18, 2023. The analysis reported on here does not use the community infrastructure entity to identify Dutch research output, but identifies research outputs directly by matching them to organisations in scope for Dutch research (see section [Dutch research organisations](#)).

Figure 2 - Schematic representation of dataset organisation of OpenAIRE

Dutch research organisations

A list of identifiers (OpenAlex IDs, OpenAIRE IDs and ROR IDs) was composed for Dutch research performing organisations (RPOs) both through manual searching and automated mapping. First, ROR IDs were identified for all RPOs through the search functionality on the ROR website. Second, the OpenAlex 'institutions' table and the OpenAIRE 'organizations' table (for OpenAlex) in Google Big Query were queried with these ROR IDs to collect the OpenAlex IDs and OpenAIRE IDs, respectively.

Identifiers were collected for the following groups of Dutch RPOs (see Appendix A):

- Universities, organised in Universities of the Netherlands⁶ (UNL, n=14);
- University Medical Centres, organised in the Dutch Federation of University Medical Centres (NFU, n=9⁷);

⁶ <https://www.universiteitenvannederland.nl/en>

⁷ including Amsterdam UMC as amalgamation of VUMC and AMC, as well as both VUMC and AMC separately

- National research institutes under the umbrella organisation of the Foundation for Dutch Scientific Research Institutes⁸ (NWO-i, n= 9);
- Research institutes of the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences⁹ (KNAW, n=10);
- Universities of Applied Sciences affiliated to the Netherlands Association of Universities of Applied Sciences (Vereniging Hogescholen)¹⁰ (VH, n=35 of 37¹¹)

For some organisations, multiple OpenAIRE IDs were linked to the organisation's ROR ID, and in one case (University of Groningen), two OpenAlex IDs were identified through matching on ROR ID. All OpenAlex IDs and OpenAIRE IDs identified through matching with ROR IDs were included in the analysis.

Importantly, only OpenAlex IDs and OpenAIRE IDs linked to an organisation's ROR were included - with the exception of the university medical centres in Amsterdam (formerly VUMC and AMC, currently Amsterdam UMC) for which also OpenAIRE IDs not linked to ROR IDs were identified and included.

Coverage of research output

Using the OpenAlex IDs and OpenAIRE IDs identified for the Dutch RPOs in scope, all research outputs (Works in OpenAlex and Publication, Dataset, Software and Other Research Output in OpenAIRE) were collected where these IDs were either included as an author affiliation (in OpenAlex) or linked with relation type 'affiliation' (OpenAIRE), and with publication year 2022 (using the fields for publication year in the respective databases).

For all research outputs collected, DOIs were included in the metadata collected from OpenAlex and OpenAIRE. In OpenAlex, 'doi' is a top level field (as well as one of the id-types in the nested top level field 'ids'). Each record in OpenAlex is matched to one DOI (or no DOI). Where multiple versions of an article are identified in OpenAlex (e.g. a preprint or an accepted author manuscript in a repository), these are listed as 'locations'. If these other versions have a DOI, this DOI is not included as an identifier for the record itself. In contrast, in OpenAIRE, multiple versions of a publication are listed as 'instances', with a set of identifiers (including DOI if available) for each instance, and the deduplicated set of identifiers for all instances listed in the field 'pid' for the record as a whole. Thus, unlike in OpenAlex, records in OpenAIRE can have multiple DOIs, representing multiple versions of the publication.

⁸ <https://www.nwo.nl/en/nwoi>

⁹ <https://knaaw.nl/en/institutes>

¹⁰

<https://www.vereniginghogescholen.nl/kennisbank/english/artikelen/list-of-universities-of-applied-sciences>

¹¹ For two Universities of Applied Sciences (Thomas More Hogeschool and Viaa University of Applied Sciences, no RORs could be identified. These organisations are therefore not included in this analysis.

For records with one or multiple DOIs collected, DOIs were matched to Crossref to collect the Crossref type (e.g. journal article, proceedings article, book chapter, dataset). This allows for the matching of records from OpenAlex and OpenAIRE on publication type, as both databases use a different classification for publication types.

The resulting data allow calculation of the number of research outputs detected in OpenAlex and OpenAIRE for each RPO or group of RPOs, and, for research outputs that include a DOI, the overlap between the two databases.

The SQL scripts used to select research outputs, collect relevant metadata and calculate aggregated data are included in the Github repository accompanying this report.

Publication types

Both OpenAlex and OpenAIRE use a bespoke classification of publication types (see Table 1).

In OpenAlex, publication type is expressed as string value in the variable 'type'. All types except 'article' follow the controlled vocabulary used in Crossref - either taken directly from Crossref, or assigned by OpenAlex for records without Crossref DOI. OpenAlex deviates from Crossref's publication type classification in couple of important ways¹²:

- As Crossref assigns publication type based on publication venue, not at the level of individual records, publication type 'journal article' in Crossref also includes non-article content such as editorials and letters. In contrast, OpenAlex has the separate publication types 'letter', 'editorial' and 'erratum' (corrections).
- OpenAlex assigns publication type 'paratext' to all records that are about the publication venue, including front-covers, back-covers, tables of contents, and the journal itself.
- OpenAlex assigns publication type 'article' to journal articles, conference proceedings and preprints, as they consider the distinctions between them to be more about where they are published or hosted, rather than about the type of publication. Within OpenAlex, a further differentiation can be made based on the type of publication venue or host venue (journal, conference, repository) and the article version.

¹² For more information, see <https://docs.openalex.org/api-entities/works/work-object#type>

Crossref (type)	OpenAlex (type)
journal-article	article
book-chapter	book-chapter
dataset	dataset
proceedings-article	paratext
posted-content	peer-review
peer-review	book
journal-issue	dissertation
other	other
book	report
component	standard
monograph	reference-entry
report	editorial
edited-book	grant
reference-entry	erratum
grant	letter
proceedings	
reference-book	
book-part	
report-component	
book-section	
report-series	
database	

Table 1A - Publication types of records from publication year 2022 in Crossref (left) and OpenAlex (right), in descending order of frequency in each database.

In OpenAIRE, multiple versions of a publication (or other main output type, like dataset, software, or 'other research product') are listed as 'instances', with each instance having its own subtype. Table 1B shows the subtypes included in OpenAIRE for research output from 2022. In this analysis, only the high-level publication types were collected, not the subtypes of individual instances.

OpenAIRE (type)	OpenAIRE (subtype)
Publication	Article
	Other literature type
	Part of book or chapter of book
	Conference object
	Preprint
	Master thesis
	Doctoral thesis
	Book
	Bachelor thesis
	Thesis
	Research
	Review
	Report
	Presentation
	External research report
	Contribution for newspaper or weekly magazine
	Project deliverable
	Journal
	Patent
	Data Management Plan
	Other ORP type
	Newsletter
	Project proposal
	Project milestone
	Data Paper
	UNKNOWN
	Lecture
	Annotation
	Software Paper
	Dataset

OpenAIRE (type)	OpenAIRE (subtype)	
Dataset	Dataset	
	Image	
	Bioentity	
	Audiovisual	
	Sound	
	Film	
	UNKNOWN	
	Clinical Trial	
	Other dataset type	
	Other ORP type	
	Software	Software
	Other Research Product	Other ORP type
UNKNOWN		
Lecture		
Research Object		
InteractiveResource		
Annotation		
PhysicalObject		
Collection		
Event		
Model		

	Clinical Trial
	Software
	Internal report
	Image

Table 1B - Publication types and subtypes of instances contained within records from publication year 2022 in OpenAIRE, in descending order of frequency within each main type.

When considering results from OpenAlex and OpenAIRE separately, the publication type classification of each database can be used. However, when combining data from OpenAlex and OpenAIRE a choice needs to be made to unambiguously assign a publication type to each record. Since for these combined analyses, records were matched on DOI, the decision was made to collect publication type from Crossref for these DOIS, and use this to compare both datasets on publication type.

Coverage of metadata types

For all research outputs identified as affiliated with Dutch RPOs in OpenAlex and OpenAIRE, a TRUE/FALSE table was generated indicating, for each record, the presence or absence of a number of metadata types in that database, as well as in Crossref (Table 2).

metadata type	Crossref field	OpenAlex field	OpenAIRE field
author_string	author.family	authorships.author.display_name	author.fullname
author_id	-	authorships.author.id	-
author_id_orcid	author.orcid	authorships.author.id	author.id.value where author.id.scheme = "orcid" or 'orcid_pending"
affiliation_string	author.affiliation.name	authorships.institutions.display_name	legalname <i>(from Organisation table)</i>
affiliation_id	-	authorships.institutions.id	id <i>(from Organisation table)</i>
affiliation_id_ror	author.affiliation.id.id where author.affiliation.id.id_type = 'ROR'	authorships.institutions.ror	pid.value where pid.scheme = 'ROR' <i>(from Organisation table)</i>
abstract	abstract	abstract_inverted_index	description ¹³
citations	is_referenced_by_count	cited_by_count	reltype.name = "IsCitedBy" <i>(from Relation table)</i>
references	references_count	referenced_works	reltype.name = "Cites" <i>(from Relation table)</i>
field	subject	concepts	subjects

¹³ The field 'description' is not reserved for abstracts, so can contain other information.

venue_string	container_title ¹⁴	primary_location. source.display_ name	container.name ¹⁵ <i>(only for Publication table)</i>
venue_id	-	primary_location. source.id	-
venue_issn	ISSN	primary_location. source.issn	container.issnOnline and/or container.issnPrinted <i>(only for Publication table)</i>
venue_issn_l	-	primary_location. source.issn_l	container.issnLinking <i>(only for Publication table)</i>
funders_string	funders.name	grant.funder_ display_name	funding.shortName <i>(from Project table)</i>
funders_id	funders.DOI	grant.funder	funding.shortName ¹⁶ <i>(from Project table)</i>
funders_id_doi	funders.DOI	_17	-

Table 2 - Metadata types included in this study, with the respective database fields in Crossref, OpenAlex and OpenAIRE used to determine presence or absence of information for each metadata type. For OpenAlex, fields are from the Works table, unless otherwise noted. For OpenAIRE, fields are from the research output tables (Publication, Dataset, Software, Other Research Product), unless otherwise noted.

Based on these data, for both databases the proportion of records was calculated that had information on each of these metadata types included, both for all records and per publication type. For records with a DOI, a direct comparison was made between coverage of specific metadata types for the same set of outputs in OpenAlex and OpenAIRE.

¹⁴ Records with type 'posted_content', 'book' and 'monograph' do not include information in the 'container_title' field).

¹⁵ For records from research output tables 'Dataset', 'Software' and 'Other Research Output', 'publisher' is used as proxy for venue_string.

¹⁶ funder names in OpenAIRE are harmonised so can be used as ids. The field 'id' in the Project table also has a funder-specific prefix that could be used for this purpose.

¹⁷ Funder DOIs are available in OpenAlex in the field 'ids.doi', in the Funder table, but were not used in this analysis

4. Coverage comparison of research output

The description of results will focus on research output of Dutch universities and university medical centres (UNL+NFU), since these constitute the majority of research outputs identified in our analysis. Results for other groups of Dutch RPOs (NWO-i, KNAW and VH) are added to give an indication of their coverage in OpenAlex and OpenAIRE, and to highlight some observed differences with UNL/NFU output.

Total research output

UNL/NFU

For publication year 2022, the total number of research outputs from Dutch universities and university medical centres (UNL/NFU) was 72,502 in OpenAlex and 83,370 in OpenAIRE¹⁸. The proportion of these records with a DOI was 99% in OpenAlex (n=72,036) and 70% in OpenAIRE (n=57,955). Since records in OpenAIRE can be associated with multiple DOIs, the total number of DOIs identified in OpenAIRE is higher than the total number of records with a DOI, namely 68,017 (Figure 3).

Publication year 2022 was chosen as the focus for this analysis, since coverage of research output from Dutch RPOs was markedly more limited for 2023 than for 2022, at least for OpenAIRE (with total number of research outputs in scope of this analysis for 2023 70.0% of the total number for 2022). In OpenAlex, the coverage of research output for 2023 was much closer to that of 2022, namely 93.7%.

UNL / NFU

Publication year 2022

¹⁸ Throughout this analysis, counts are deduplicated across organisations in each grouping, e.g. a record (or DOI) identified as output of Utrecht University and University of Groningen is counted once in the total output for UNL. Fractionalized counting has not been applied.

Figure 3 - Research outputs (DOIs and non-DOIs) from Dutch universities and university medical centres (UNL/NFU) in OpenAlex and OpenAIRE. Research outputs are deduplicated on database ID and DOI.

While at first glance, the number of outputs with DOIs seems similar in OpenAlex and OpenAIRE, with OpenAIRE primarily having more research outputs without DOIs, the picture becomes somewhat more nuanced when looking at individual RPOs, and comparing universities and university medical centres (Figure 4).

Figure 4 - Number of research outputs (publication year 2022) for Dutch universities (UNL, left) and university medical centres (NFU, right) in OpenAlex and OpenAIRE. For abbreviations see Appendix 1.

Here, it becomes apparent that for some universities (such as Delft University of Technology (TUD), Leiden University (LU), University Maastricht (MU), Free University (VU) and Wageningen University & Research (WUR), the number of research outputs identified in OpenAIRE is larger than in OpenAlex, both for records with and without DOIs. For some

other universities (such as Erasmus University Rotterdam (EUR) and University of Groningen (RUG), and for many university medical centres (with the exception of VUMC and LUMC), the situation is reversed, with more research outputs identified in OpenAlex than in OpenAIRE.

One explanation for the differences between universities, especially regarding identification of affiliated output in OpenAIRE, is the increased attention in 2022-2023 (as part of the implementation of the Dutch Research Portal in OpenAIRE) to get university repositories and CRIS systems registered as content providers in OpenAIRE, and optimise configurations for harvesting. In addition, organisations may differ in which part of an organisation's research output is made available for harvesting may also differ - especially when harvesting is done from the institutional repository rather than the institution's CRIS. Where universities and university medical centres each maintain their own instances of CRIS-systems and/or repositories, this may also explain differences observed in the ratio of identified research output in OpenAlex and OpenAIRE between some universities and their university medical centres, such as for Utrecht University (UU) and University Medical Centre Utrecht (UMCU).

Finally, the case of the university medical centres associated with the two Dutch universities in Amsterdam (AMC and VUMC) is a special one, as since 2018, they have merged into Amsterdam UMC¹⁹ (AUMC). Amsterdam UMC has its own ROR ID, with the constituting university medical centres listed as child organisations that each still have their own ROR ID as well. All three entities also have separate IDs in both OpenAlex and OpenAIRE (see Appendix 1). From Figure 4, it becomes apparent that OpenAlex and OpenAIRE currently deal with this situation differently. In OpenAlex, research output from AMC and VUMC is primarily assigned to Amsterdam UMC in OpenAlex, with a subset also assigned to AMC and VUMC, which in OpenAlex are classified as child institutions to Amsterdam UMC. In contrast, in OpenAIRE, research outputs from VUMC are assigned to that organisation's own OpenAIRE ID, and Amsterdam UMC has virtually no research output associated with it (yet).

Because research output from university medical centres is usually included in output reported by universities (e.g. in providing KUOZ²⁰ data to UNL, or for national open access monitoring), for the remainder of this report, research output from universities and their medical centres will be combined into one dataset per university, deduplicated on database IDs and DOIs. Data for AUMC will be presented separately as not all AUMC output can be unambiguously assigned to AMC and/or VUMC.

¹⁹ <https://www.amsterdamumc.org/en/organization/amsterdam-umc.htm>

²⁰ Kengetallen Universitair Onderzoek -

https://www.universiteitenvannederland.nl/files/publications/VSNU_Definitieafspraken_onderzoeksinzet_en_output_KUOZ.PDF

NWO-i, KNAW & VH

While for most universities and at least some university medical centres, coverage in OpenAIRE matches or exceeds that in OpenAlex, as reflected in the combined data for UNL and NFU (Figure 3-4), for both NWO-i and VH as a whole, more research output is identified in OpenAlex than in OpenAIRE (Figure 5). In contrast, for KNAW, the total number of research outputs is comparable in both databases. Factors playing into these results may be the use of CRIS systems and institutional repositories, and the extent to which these are made available to harvest.

Figure 5 - Number of research outputs (publication year 2022) for national research institutes under the umbrella organisation of the Foundation for Dutch Scientific Research Institutes (NWO-i, n= 9); Research institutes of the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW, n=10); and Universities of Applied Sciences (VH, n=35). Research outputs are deduplicated on database ID and DOI within each group.

Looking at individual research organisations in these groups more in detail (Figures 6-7), it is again clear that there are large differences between organisations in the coverage of research outputs. Many organisations have very low numbers of detected research output in both databases, which may at least partly reflect the actual situation (especially for VH organisations with less emphasis on research). Another explanation could be that publishing is done in formats and venues that are not included in bibliographic databases, including OpenAlex and OpenAIRE. In those cases where OpenAlex detects more research outputs than OpenAIRE, this could be related to the extent to which organisations do or do not have institutional repositories and/or CRIS, the extent to which these are utilised, and the extent to which they have been optimised for harvesting by OpenAIRE.

In this context, the variability of coverage in OpenAIRE (as compared to OpenAlex) among KNAW institutes is notable, since KNAW provided a CRIS system for all its institutions²¹. In general, coverage of research output from KNAW institutes in OpenAIRE is low compared to OpenAlex, with the exception of the Netherlands Institute of Ecology (NIOO). Closer

²¹ See <https://pure.knaw.nl/portal/> for the joint research portal of all KNAW institutes

inspection revealed that the majority of NIOO output in OpenAIRE (n=739 of 932) concerns datasets, predominantly in DataverseNL (n=697).

Finally, another reason for inclusion of research outputs from NWO-i, KNAW and VH organisations (especially in OpenAIRE) could be because they are articles (and other output types) co-authored with researchers from Dutch universities or university medical centres, and thus captured through harvesting repositories or CRIS systems of these collaboration organisations.

Figure 6 - Number of research outputs (publication year 2022) for national research institutes under the umbrella organisation of the Foundation for Dutch Scientific Research Institutes (NWO-i, n= 9) and Research institutes of the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW, n=10). Research outputs are deduplicated on database ID and DOI within each group. For abbreviations see Appendix 1.

VH

publication year 2022

VH

publication year 2022

- OpenAlex - dois
- OpenAlex - non-dois
- OpenAIRE - dois
- OpenAIRE - non-dois

Figure 7 - Number of research outputs (publication year 2022) for Universities of Applied Sciences (VH, n=35). Research outputs are deduplicated on database ID and DOI within each group. For abbreviations see Appendix 1.

Publication types

Since OpenAIRE and OpenAlex use different classification systems for publication types (see Methodology section), the coverage of publication types in both databases cannot be compared directly. Looking at both databases separately for the different groups used in this analysis (UNL/NFU, NWO-i, KNAW and VH), it is clear that the majority of research outputs identified in both databases is textual material - publication types 'articles' and 'book-chapter' in OpenAlex, and type 'publication' in OpenAIRE (Table 3,4).

In OpenAlex, datasets only make up a small percentage (0.4% for UNL/NFU and 0.8% for KNAW). In OpenAIRE, datasets make up a higher percentage of records with DOI (3.1% for UNL/NFU and 67.1% for KNAW - the latter attributable to NIOO, as discussed above). Among non-DOIs in OpenAIRE, there is also a notable percentage of records with type 'Other research output' (6.2% for UNL/NFU, 4.4% for NWO-i and 31.3% for KNAW).

OpenAlex	UNL / NFU (n=72,502)	NWO-i (n=1856)	KNAW (n=1027)	VH (n=2303)
article	92.3%	93.8%	91.0%	91.3%
book-chapter	5.1%	3.3%	5.6%	7.0%
peer-review	0.6%	1.8%	0.8%	0.1%
dataset	0.4%	-	0.8%	-
editorial	0.4%	0.1%	0.2%	0.5%
report	0.3%	0.3%	0.5%	0.5%
paratext	0.3%	0.4%	0.1%	0.4%
book	0.2%	0.1%	0.3%	0.0%
other	0.2%	0.1%	0.4%	0.1%
erratum	0.1%	0.1%	0.2%	0.1%
letter	0.0%	-	-	-
dissertation	0.0%	0.1%	0.2%	-
reference-entry	0.0%	-	-	-

Table 3 - Frequency of publication types of records (publication year 2022) in OpenAlex for UNL/NFU, NWO-i, KNAW and VH. In each group, 99-100% of records have DOIs. Note: publication type 'articles' in OpenAlex includes conference proceedings and preprints.

OpenAIRE (DOIs)	UNL / NFU (n=68,017)	NWO-i (n=1356)	KNAW (n=1056)	VH (n=1174)
publication	96.9%	100.0%	33.0%	100.0%
dataset	3.1%	-	67.0%	-
software	0.0%	-	-	-
other	0.0%	-	-	-

OpenAIRE (non-DOIs)	UNL / NFU (n=25,415)	NWO-i (n=114)	KNAW (n=112)	VH (n=76)
publication	93.1%	95.6%	39.3%	100.0%
dataset	0.7%	-	28.6%	-
software	0.0%	-	0.9%	-
other	6.2%	4.4%	31.3%	-

Table 4 - Frequency of main publication types of DOIs (top) and non-DOIs (bottom) (publication year 2022) in OpenAIRE for UNL/NFU, NWO-i, KNAW and VH. other = 'Other research output'.

Overlap between databases

Comparing coverage of research output from OpenAlex and OpenAIRE side-by-side gives initial information about the number of research outputs in each database. However, it does not provide information about the extent to which the two sets of research outputs overlap (i.e. the same research outputs are identified in both databases as belonging to the same research organisation(s)), or instead, are unique to each database. To further investigate the overlap between research output in OpenAlex and OpenAIRE for Dutch RPOs, records identified from both databases were matched on DOI only - no additional fuzzy matching on e.g. title, authors and/or publication venue was attempted. Aggregated data for this part of the analysis are included in Appendix 2.

When two records match for a particular Dutch RPO (or group of RPOs), this means that it is attributed to that RPO (or group of RPOs) in both databases. It is important to note that there are two main reasons why records might have no match in the other database: either it is not present in the other database at all, or, when it is present, it is not attributed to the particular RPO or group of RPOs in that database. While for retrieval purposes, the effect is the same (the record will not be retrieved from that database), the potential ways to improve coverage are very different: in the first case, the database would need to expand its coverage, in the second case, it would need to improve identification of affiliated organisations (and matching to its list of organisation ids). Finally, the fact that a record is identified as belonging to a specific RPO (or group of RPOs) in one database but not the other, can indicate an error or omission in either database: either it is missing or not assigned correctly in the second database, or incorrectly assigned in the first.

UNL / NFU

When looking at the overlap between OpenAlex and OpenAIRE for research output (publication year 2022) attributed for UNL / NFU (Figure 8), it becomes apparent that even though the total number of DOIs from both databases is more or less comparable (n=72,036 in OpenAlex, n=68,017 in OpenAIRE), only 50,688 of DOIs is identified in both databases as being affiliated with a Dutch university or university medical centre (green bar segments in Figure 8). This means that 29.6% of retrieved DOIs for this group in OpenAlex and 25.5% of retrieved DOIs in OpenAIRE are retrieved uniquely from that database (light grey and light blue bar segments in Figure 8).

It should be noted that in a small number of cases, publications are assigned a different publication year in both databases, and for that reason will not be retrieved from both databases when filtering on a specific publication year, even though it is assigned the same affiliation in both databases. Such publications are indicated in light green in Figure 7 and all subsequent charts in this section, and included in reported counts on overlap.

In addition to DOIs retrieved from one or both databases, Figure 8 also depicts the number publications (or other output types) without DOI, which is very small in OpenAlex (n= 363, dark grey bar segment) but of considerable size in OpenAIRE (n=25,514, dark blue bar segment).

Overlap OpenAlex - OpenAIRE

publication year 2022

Figure 8 - Overlap between OpenAlex and OpenAIRE of records (publication year 2022) for UNL/NFU. Records were matched on DOI.

Zooming in on individual universities (together with their university medical centre, where applicable), for all universities, there is some proportion of research output that is identified uniquely in OpenAlex and in OpenAIRE, respectively (Figure 8). The percentage of research output identified in OpenAlex that is uniquely identified in that database varies from 13.9% (Open University, OU) to 64.5% (Erasmus University, EUR). For OpenAIRE, this percentage varies from 15.5% (EUR) to 50.4% (Free University, VU) when looking at DOIs only, and from 25.3% to 66.9% (for the same two institutions) when also including non-DOIs.

As mentioned in the section on total number of research outputs, the situation for Amsterdam University Medical Centres (AUMC) is a special one - the very high proportion of outputs uniquely identified from OpenAlex can at least partly be explained by the differences between OpenAlex and OpenAIRE in how research outputs from AMC and VUMC are assigned.

Overlap OpenAlex - OpenAIRE

UNL / NFU, publication year 2022

Figure 9 - Overlap between OpenAlex and OpenAIRE of records (publication year 2022) for individual universities (with their university medical centre, where applicable). Records were matched on DOI.

NWO-i, KNAW and VH

For other groups of Dutch RPOs, the overlap between research outputs retrieved from OpenAlex and OpenAIRE is (even) less than for UNL/NFU (Figure 10). The percentage of research outputs retrieved from OpenAlex that is unique for that database is 51.8% for NWO-i, 70.3% for KNAW and 59.5% for VH. OpenAIRE has 39.3% unique records for NWO-i and 73.8% for KNAW (both DOIs and non-DOIs). For VH, more research outputs identified in OpenAIRE were also identified in OpenAlex, with only 25.8% unique to OpenAIRE.

Overlap OpenAlex - OpenAIRE

publication year 2022

Figure 10 - Overlap between OpenAlex and OpenAIRE of records (publication year 2022) for NWO-i, KNAW and VH. Records were matched on DOI.

As with universities, there are large differences between individual organisations among NWO-i and KNAW and VH (Figure 11, 12). In some cases (eg. ARCNL and NSCR within NWO-i, and Westerdijk Institute within KNAW), almost all research input identified in OpenAIRE was also identified in OpenAlex. In other cases, a considerable portion of research output is identified only from OpenAlex or OpenAIRE, respectively. As also seen in the section on total research output, in almost all cases, more research outputs are identified in OpenAlex than in OpenAIRE, with the exception of NIOO (KNAW), and two Universities of Applied Sciences (VH): HAN University of Applied Sciences (HAN) and Hanze University of Applied Sciences (Hanze). For VH in particular, there are also a number of organisations for which almost no research output was identified in either OpenAlex or OpenAIRE.

Overlap OpenAlex - OpenAIRE

NWO-i, publication year 2022

Overlap OpenAlex - OpenAIRE

KNAW, publication year 2022

Legend for Figure 11:
 - OpenAlex with DOI (light grey)
 - OpenAlex without DOI (dark grey)
 - both - OpenAlex different year (light green)
 - OpenAlex and OpenAIRE (medium green)
 - both - OpenAIRE different year (darker green)
 - OpenAIRE with DOI (blue)
 - OpenAIRE without DOI (dark blue)

Figure 11 - Overlap between OpenAlex and OpenAIRE of records (publication year 2022) for individual NWO-i (left) and KNAW (right) institutes. Records were matched on DOI.

Overlap OpenAlex - OpenAIRE

VH, publication year 2022

Overlap OpenAlex - OpenAIRE

VH, publication year 2022

Legend for Figure 12:
 - OpenAlex with DOI (light grey)
 - OpenAlex without DOI (dark grey)
 - both - OpenAlex different year (light green)
 - OpenAlex and OpenAIRE (medium green)
 - both - OpenAIRE different year (darker green)
 - OpenAIRE with DOI (blue)
 - OpenAIRE without DOI (dark blue)

Figure 12 - Overlap between OpenAlex and OpenAIRE of records (publication year 2022) for individual Universities of Applied Sciences (VH). Records were matched on DOI.

Publication types

For research output with DOIs, not only is it possible to assess the overlap between OpenAlex and OpenAIRE, but also to break this overlap down by publication type. While OpenAlex and OpenAIRE use different publication type classifications, by matching DOIs back to Crossref and collecting the Crossref publication type for each DOI, the same publication type classification can be used for OpenAlex and OpenAIRE records. In this way, it is also possible to identify non-Crossref DOIs, as no publication type will be retrieved for these from Crossref. In this report, this analysis was performed for UNL/NFU output only. Aggregated data for this part of the analysis are included in Appendix 3.

Unsurprisingly, the large majority of DOIs identified in either OpenAlex or OpenAIRE for UNL / NFU had Crossref type 'journal article' (n= 65,501 of 91,808, or 70.9%). Most journal articles (or other research output labelled as such in Crossref) retrieved from OpenAIRE were also retrieved from OpenAlex, with only 10.4% of DOIs from OpenAIRE uniquely retrieved from this database (Figure 13). For OpenAlex, 27.2% of DOIs in this group were uniquely retrieved from OpenAlex.

Overlap OpenAlex - OpenAIRE

UNL / NFU publication year 2022 (DOIs only) - Crossref type

Figure 13 - Overlap between OpenAlex and OpenAIRE of records (publication year 2022) for UNL / NFU, for Crossref publication type 'journal article'. Only records with DOI are included.

Next to journal articles, the most common Crossref publication types were posted content (which includes preprints), book chapters and proceeding articles (Figure 14). Regarding overlap between OpenAlex and OpenAIRE, posted content and book chapters follow a similar pattern as journal articles, while for proceeding articles, relatively few records were retrieved uniquely from OpenAlex compared to the other publication types.

Non-Crossref DOIs constitute 12.7% (n=11,687 of 91,808) of all DOIs retrieved from OpenAlex and OpenAIRE (Figure 14). The large majority of these are retrieved from OpenAIRE only, which is consistent with OpenAlex not yet including DOIs from DOI registrars other than Crossref, such as DataCite. Based on the publication types of DOIs in OpenAIRE (Table 4), these DOIs are indeed expected to include a considerable proportion of datasets, but can also include other publication types.

Overlap OpenAlex - OpenAIRE

UNL / NFU publication year 2022 (DOIs only) - Crossref type

Figure 14 - Overlap between OpenAlex and OpenAIRE of records (publication year 2022) for UNL / NFU, by Crossref publication type. Only records with DOI are included. Crossref publication types (other than 'journal article') with > 1000 records are shown.

Finally, among other publication types with more than 100 DOIs in the combined research output from OpenAlex and OpenAIRE for UNL / NFU, dissertations are the most common, followed by peer reviews (Figure 15). Datasets (those included in Crossref), books and monographs and the non-descript 'other' make up the remaining publication types. Of the most common publication types in this group, dissertations are exclusively retrieved from OpenAIRE, while peer reviews are more often retrieved from OpenAlex, with 81.6% of records of this publication type identified in OpenAlex uniquely retrieved from this database.

Overlap OpenAlex - OpenAIRE

UNL / NFU publication year 2022 (DOIs only) - Crossref type

Figure 15 - Overlap between OpenAlex and OpenAIRE of records (publication year 2022) for UNL / NFU, by Crossref publication type. Only records with DOI are included. Crossref publication types between 100 and 1000 records are shown.

Discussion & Conclusions

For identifying research output from Dutch RPOs based on ROR IDs, OpenAlex and OpenAIRE currently are complementary resources, with only partial overlap in records that are assigned to Dutch RPOs. For publication year 2022, OpenAlex almost exclusively returns research output with Crossref DOIs, while OpenAIRE also contains a considerable proportion of records without DOI that are identified as affiliated with Dutch RPOs, as well as records with non-Crossref DOIs.

Among records with Crossref DOIs, dissertations are retrieved exclusively from OpenAIRE, while for many other publication types, including journal articles, book chapters, preprints and peer reviews, more unique records are retrieved from OpenAlex than from OpenAIRE, although OpenAIRE also has unique records for all these publication types.

While for most universities and at least some university medical centres, as well as for many NWO-i institutes, coverage in OpenAIRE (in total number of records) matches or exceeds that in OpenAlex, most KNAW institutes seem less well represented in OpenAIRE than in OpenAlex. Universities of Applied Sciences (VH) differ greatly in the amount of research output they produce. Where they do produce research output, this is usually found in both OpenAlex and OpenAIRE, with, in most cases, more unique records identified in OpenAlex than in OpenAIRE.

It is important to note that there are two main reasons why records might not be retrieved from a particular database (including OpenAlex and OpenAIRE) when filtering on research output from particular RPOs: either it is not present in the database at all, or, when it is present, it is not attributed to that specific RPO. While for retrieval purposes, the effect is the same, the potential ways for improvement are very different. In the first case, the database would need to expand its coverage, in the second case, it would need to improve identification of affiliated organisations (and matching to its list of organisation ids). Finally, the fact that a record is identified as belonging to a specific RPO in a database could also mean it is incorrectly assigned to that organisation. It should be noted that both OpenAlex and OpenAIRE are in active development, and improvements (esp. in affiliation detection) are to be expected in future iterations of the databases.

In comparing coverage and retrieval of Dutch RPOs in OpenAlex and OpenAIRE, both the effects of different coverage (i.e. in the case of most non-Crossref DOIs and non-DOIs), as well as potential differences in the identification of affiliated institutions (i.e. for Crossref DOIs that are only retrieved from one of both databases) are observed.

5. Data flows

OpenAlex and OpenAIRE both aggregate metadata from various sources, perform steps to clean, combine, consolidate and enrich this information, and then make the resulting dataset available as open research information through their various interfaces (web interface, API, and/or data snapshots). Understanding how information on Dutch research outputs is collected and enriched by both databases can help assess where possible 'loops' exist in data flows (e.g. where information flows from institutional information systems to aggregators, which are then used again to enrich institutional information systems), where information can best be enriched and by whom, and where existing 'gaps' are in open metadata.

This chapter provides a narrative description of data flows in OpenAlex and OpenAIRE. An empirical analysis of data flows of Dutch research outputs into these two databases will be added in a future version of this report.

OpenAlex

OpenAlex collects information on research outputs (works), authors, institutions, funders, publishers, sources (including journals and repositories) and concepts (see Figure 16) from a variety of sources.

Figure 16 - OpenAlex entities overview. Image source: OpenAlex technical information²².

²² <https://docs.openalex.org/api-entities/entities-overview>

According to OpenAlex' documentation²³, their two most important data sources are Microsoft Academic Graph (for historical data, i.e. information on research outputs published prior to MAG's closure in December 2021) and Crossref, with other key sources including:

- ORCID
- ROR
- DOAJ
- Unpaywall
- Pubmed
- Pubmed Central
- The ISSN International Centre
- Internet Archive
- Web crawls
- Subject-area and institutional repositories

New research outputs ('Works') are primarily collected from Crossref and PubMed, with links between works and other entities created by parsing work metadata in structured form (eg, in the Crossref API) or unstructured form (eg, on a publisher landing page) (Priem, Piwowar and Orr, 2022).

For affiliation information, affiliation strings obtained from both structured and unstructured sources are extracted and normalised, using an algorithm that combines both rules-based and machine-learning stages (Priem, Piwowar and Orr, 2022, French and Buttrick, 2023, OpenAlex white paper²⁴). Through this process, affiliations are matched to OpenAlex' 'institution' entities, which for each institution has standardised information including ROR ID.

Institutions are linked to works via the "authorship" object, meaning that each author can have one or more affiliations linked to them. Where multiple versions of an article are identified in OpenAlex (e.g. a preprint or an accepted author manuscript in a repository), these are listed as 'locations', which do not have authorship information directly linked to them.

Three important questions surround the data flow of publications and associated affiliation information into OpenAlex:

1. Are new works only obtained from Crossref and PubMed, with only additional information (like affiliation metadata and locations) retrieved from other sources (like publisher websites and repositories), or are new works themselves also directly identified from these sources?
2. Is (structured or unstructured) affiliation information from alternative locations (e.g. preprints or accepted versions in a repository) also used to link works to institutions, or only affiliation information from the primary location of the work?

²³ <https://docs.openalex.org/additional-help/faq#where-does-your-data-come-from>

²⁴ OpenAlex: End-to-End Process for Institution Parsing
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ppbKRVtyneWc7Hjpo8TOm57YLGx1C2Oo>

3. Is structured affiliation information beyond affiliation strings (like ROR IDs in Crossref) also ingested into OpenAlex, or are only raw affiliation used for matching to OpenAlex institution entities?

OpenAlex documentation is not fully conclusive about this. It is mentioned that new works themselves are also collected from institutional and discipline-specific repositories (eg, arXiv)²⁵ (see also Priem, Piwovar and Orr, 2022). Through personal communication, it was learned that OpenAlex ingests data from other sources (institutional repositories mainly) but then uses web-scraping on the landing pages to get the affiliations for those sources.

This might imply that information from repositories is used as primary source for new works, and/or that affiliation information from repositories (either structured information via OAI-PMH endpoints, or unstructured information via landing pages) is used for matching works to institution entities.

²⁵ <https://docs.openalex.org/api-entities/works>

OpenAIRE

As a database, OpenAIRE is structured somewhat differently from OpenAlex. The relational data structure of the OpenAIRE Graph (at least as reflected in the data snapshot) has been briefly discussed in the Methodology section. Conceptually, OpenAIRE distinguishes entities for research products (publications, datasets, software and other research products), organisations and projects (linked to funders), with ‘data sources’ as a separate entity class (Manghi et al., 2019, OpenAIRE Graph Documentation²⁶). Figure 17 provides a schematic representation of the entities and relations in the OpenAIRE Graph, focusing on relations between research outputs and affiliated organisations, as this is the scope of this study.

Figure 17 OpenAIRE entities and types of relations between data sources, organisations and research products. Image source: OpenAIRE Documentation (v5.1.1)²⁷ (modified to add relations).

Metadata about entities and the links between them are harvested from data sources such as institutional repositories, data/software repositories, publishers and registries (including Crossref and DataCite). Through text mining of abstracts and, for Open Access articles, full texts additional links between entities are inferred to enrich the graph. Provenance is tracked at two levels: 1) at the level of full entities, as a variable in the relation between entity and data source, 2) at the level of specific elements within entities, for instance for author PIDs (ORCID), subjects and country in the entity ‘publications’. The provenance variable indicates *how* information is derived (e.g. harvested, inferred by OpenAIRE), not *where* the information is derived from. The latter is available in the form of relations between data sources and research products and between data sources and organisations, although these do not indicate the specific sources of affiliation links (= the relations between organisations and research products).

²⁶ <https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/data-model/>

²⁷ <https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/5.1.1/data-model/>

One additional thing to note is that different versions of a publication (or other research product) are listed as 'instances' within each research product record, with some metadata (including DOI if available) specified at the level of the instance, and some others (like authors and subject(s)) at the level of the record as a whole (Figure 18). Importantly, data sources are only linked to the record as a whole (as relation type 'provides' or 'hosts', not to individual instances within the records).

Figure 18 OpenAIRE entities: instances as elements of research products. Image source: OpenAIRE Documentation (v5.1.1)²⁸ (modified to add relations).

Given OpenAIRE's data structure, there are three areas where the provenance of information on coverage of research output can be analysed:

- Data sources for research products
- Data sources for organisations
- Affiliation relations between research products and organisations

Exploring provenance of these three entities can provide empirical evidence of data flows for Dutch research output into OpenAIRE, including the various data sources information on Dutch research output is collected from.

²⁸ <https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/5.1.1/data-model/>

6. Recommendations

Considering the availability of metadata for Dutch research output in open data sources as reported here, the following recommendations are made for research organisations, funders and central organisations as UKB and UNL. These recommendations also closely align with the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information (Kramer, Neylon and Waltman, 2024).

- **Open metadata sources provide an opportunity to transition away from closed information sources**
 - Research organisations, funders and central organisations as UKB and UNL should start using open metadata sources to enrich CRIS systems and centralised data collections as UKBSis, with an eye towards replacing proprietary systems as primary sources of research information.
 - Research organisations should accompany this transition with financial support for open metadata sources to sustain their operations and further development.

- **Open metadata sources are complementary in record coverage and metadata coverage**
 - Research organisations, funders and central organisations as UKB and UNL should make use of the availability and interoperability of open metadata sources and not rely solely on one data source (e.g. to fill or enrich CRIS systems, in creating new collections of data, or to perform analysis using research information)
 - As part of the Open Science Agenda UNL, further investigation into the extent open metadata sources each cover and complement existing information in CRIS systems of research organisations, as well as centralised data collections as UKBSis, is recommended.

- **PIDs facilitate retrieval, matching and enrichment of records**
 - As much as possible, metadata records should contain or be enriched with persistent identifiers (PIDs) for research outputs, contributors, organisations and funders - both in CRIS systems, centralised data collections (eg UKBSis) and third-party open metadata sources.
 - For research output without DOIs or ISBNs, inclusion and use of other identifiers (such as handles or OAI identifiers), should be considered to prevent exclusion of parts of the research output of an organisation.

- **Institutions can improve coverage of 'their' research output in open metadata sources, increasing value for everyone**
 - Research organisations and funders should ensure the information made available to open metadata sources (e.g. through OAI-PMH or API endpoints) is as complete as possible, both in coverage of records as in coverage of metadata (including PIDs)

- Research organisations and funders, as well central organisations as UKB or UNL should work with open metadata sources (either directly by submitting and discussing issues, or more systematically by participating in governance, where possible) to improve coverage and quality of research output.
- **Institutions can put pressure on other stakeholders (esp. publishers) to improve availability of open metadata**
 - In negotiations with publishers and other primary providers of metadata, specific clauses should be included on provision of complete metadata (including PIDs for contributors, organisations and funders). Such metadata should not just be provided to research organisations participating in the agreement, but made openly available (e.g. via Crossref or DataCite). Existing publisher agreements (e.g. from JISC) provide sample language that could be re-used.
 - Where research organisations, funders and central organisations as UKB or UNL participate in initiatives with publishers and third parties to increase the coverage of metadata for their research output, this should include the condition that this enriched metadata is made openly available (e.g. through updating Crossref and DataCite records).

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8. Data availability

This pilot has made use of [Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative \(COKI\)](https://github.com/The-Academic-Observatory) infrastructure, which is documented on GitHub: <https://github.com/The-Academic-Observatory>. Here, a number of open data sources (including Crossref, OpenAlex and OpenAIRE) are ingested into a Google Big Query environment, which can then be queried via SQL.

The SQL scripts used to select research outputs, collect relevant metadata and calculate aggregated data will be made available in the accompanying Github repository: https://github.com/bmkramer/open_metadata_research_output_NL.

Record level data as well as aggregated data underlying the figures and tables in this report will be made available in the accompanying dataset: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11360571>.

Appendices

Appendix 1

Dutch RPOs with ROR ID, OpenAlex ID and OpenAIRE ID

RPO name	acronym	group	ROR ID	OpenAlex ID	OpenAIRE ID	notes
Delft University of Technology	TUD	UNL	02e2c7k09	I98358874	openorgs_::5e6bf8962665cdd040341171e5c631d8	
Eindhoven University of Technology	TUE	UNL	02c2kyt77	I83019370	openorgs_::db787c50cf46f2b08e69f830e292e42d	
Erasmus University Rotterdam	EUR	UNL	057w15z03	I913958620	openorgs_::2f735203eb40d8389a881e874bee537a	
Leiden University	UL	UNL	027bh9e22	I121797337	openorgs_::e42580548da4a1d39bb67b60b971056e, pending_org_::8489219891379f7f31ea010ae940e61d	multiple OpenAIRE IDs
Maastricht University	UNIMAAS	UNL	02jz4aj89	I34352273	openorgs_::a7e0018f6064f0dab7a8c9a48a61a1c6, pending_org_::4d8e160e153a61e0e569ebf129577a1e	multiple OpenAIRE IDs

RPO name	acronym	group	ROR ID	OpenAlex ID	OpenAIRE ID	notes
Open University	OU	UNL	018dfmf50	17876267	openorgs_::54f2e88f3eb801dc7e49a4ca90fdd1b6	
Radboud University Nijmegen	RU	UNL	016xsfp80	1145872427	openorgs_::a3af79fec4d09764e56cd6d4df1d976a, pending_org_::b7587eb8d95a6c85a12ca952079a60b4	multiple OpenAIRE IDs
Tilburg University	TiU	UNL	04b8v1s79	1193700539	openorgs_::b12b585c23a2b443b35cb33f57309a34	
University of Amsterdam	UVA	UNL	04dkp9463	1887064364	openorgs_::58f65ed1ce3c9166e9c5f939bfdbf83a	
University of Groningen	RUG	UNL	012p63287	1169381384	openorgs_::81371ea94b1a09d3243e73d6ec3527ec, pending_org_::029bd302b23537758eb9f9443cfb84f2	multiple OpenAIRE IDs
University of Twente	UVT	UNL	006hf6230	194624287	openorgs_::604881198363fedbb5d5478f465305f2	
Utrecht University	UU	UNL	04pp8hn57	1193662353	openorgs_::3d57a5aadd2e0925bca78515278f2405, pending_org_::3f083b4fea995578fd5230593a1ecd29	multiple OpenAIRE IDs
Vrije Universiteit (Free University)	VU	UNL	008xxew50	1865915315	openorgs_::1624ff7c01bb641b91f4518539a0c28a	
Wageningen University & Research	WUR	UNL	04qw24q55	1913481162	openorgs_::ad8f981707a4a1d6c9e9ee60c02b9a11	

RPO name	acronym	group	ROR ID	OpenAlex ID	OpenAIRE ID	notes
Amsterdam Medical Centre	AMC	NFU	03t4gr691	I2802928900	openorgs_::fe49cd5c84da7a89da723e24cadeb99d, pending_org_::934cae8c1579b83a115e84e9be770f18	multiple OpenAIRE IDs
Amsterdam UMC	AmsterdamUMC	NFU	05grdy37	I4210151833	openorgs_::2ce10b2528220091bd0363c1e39394c1, pending_org_::8c230cbb8481b6ebb17a869407edf882	multiple OpenAIRE IDs; pending_org ID does not include ROR
ErasmusMC	ErasmusMC	NFU	018906e22	I2801952686	openorgs_::51609e11886740e4cf5f77d0f516a43c, pending_org_::f57edef2957976fa31746dfa3b89b3	multiple OpenAIRE IDs
LUMC	LUMC	NFU	05xvt9f17	I2800006345	openorgs_::2eeca4f78f2a04a35057c1fa7918e23b, pending_org_::048d494029c90e17d1403b42a215394e	multiple OpenAIRE IDs
MaastrichtMC	MaastrichtMC	NFU	02d9ce178	I2800191616	openorgs_::3c2c37b7745ae3202347c3fa594bc66a	
Radboud University Nijmegen Medical Centre	RadboudUMC	NFU	05wg1m734	I2802934949	openorgs_::6c50ead5f8f9cac29c4c3066df9fba45, pending_org_::1cf25d5d724e3add709843ad245842ae, pending_org_::30cb991888338e8a1205dd4e9c63270	multiple OpenAIRE IDs
UMCG	UMCG	NFU	03cv38k47	I1334415907	openorgs_::e1c228979333191a8f4bd6b5f5d01644,	multiple OpenAIRE IDs

RPO name	acronym	group	ROR ID	OpenAlex ID	OpenAIRE ID	notes
					pending_org ::36274daf325aea83489d660f965fec02, pending_org ::4fd4829ae71cf5e2b9ce35cf4718e1ed	
UMCU	UMCU	NFU	0575yy874	I3018483916	openorgs___::81b64115eb383a27a9c1820a2c760c89	
VUMC	VUMC	NFU	00q6h8f30	I911458345	openorgs___::df96ffc1951dc9bc14b0695e3297f6e1, pending_org ::f6afc202892a64ccec1e51534c5f094c	multiple OpenAIRE IDs; pending_org ID does not include ROR
AMOLF, Physics of functional complex matter	AMOLF	NWO-i	038x9td67	I2803035111	openorgs___::990dcc0a2b128304fdde55df641a47b4	
ARCNL, Advanced Research Center for Nanolithography	ARCNL	NWO-i	04xe7ws48	I4210145651	openorgs___::4bfe0847ab9fa240154a274f13fa7ce0	
ASTRON, Netherlands Institute for Radio Astronomy	ASTRON	NWO-i	000k1q888	I922237871	openorgs___::bc3c03a56c8ac610e083f74395896ed4	
DIFFER, Dutch Institute for Fundamental Energy Research	DIFFER	NWO-i	03w5dn804	I4210147097	openorgs___::79a0e60afef2e753b0dc12425ecb3f8c	
National Research Institute for	CWI	NWO-i	00x7ekv49	I1341640284	openorgs___::47f4fbfcef93eb928361dffa	

RPO name	acronym	group	ROR ID	OpenAlex ID	OpenAIRE ID	notes
Mathematics and Computer Science					abd03b54	
Nikhef, National Institute of subatomic physics	NIKHEF	NWO-i	00f9tz983	I4210093566	openorgs_::e2d0ca0969cf3610d277907a57b8ae7e	
NIOZ, Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research	NIOZ	NWO-i	01gntjh03	I4210107283	openorgs_::eb2f1247784acef155801d95b5ac937b	
NSCR, Netherlands Institute for the Study of Crime and Law Enforcement	NSCR	NWO-i	03124pm05	I4210124189	openorgs_::917ca88ffc8c464dc902998c0d89c24e	
SRON, Netherlands Institute for Space Research	SRON	NWO-i	02wc0kq10	I49206369	openorgs_::1eaec9171998c0db1b627afe4a969430	
Hubrecht Institute for Developmental Biology and Stem Cell Research	HUBRECHT	KNAW	023qc4a07	I4210115206	openorgs_::1820f7ff911f4cf656fd63fd17b2fea8	
Huygens ING	HUYGENS	KNAW	04x6kq749	I2801908541	openorgs_::af7d4ec9149a9d4f43affdd3a5f6ade, pending_org_::6adaa6f7744be4606d1a4d25631b2223	multiple OpenAIRE IDs
International	IISH	KNAW	05dq4pp56	I932564295	openorgs_::a8369fe646a573e841439d	

RPO name	acronym	group	ROR ID	OpenAlex ID	OpenAIRE ID	notes
Institute of Social History (IISH)					2c24396b49	
Meertens Institute	MEERTENS	KNAW	05kaxyq51	I4210158762	openorgs_::f58b02a65440082244bedce6c5edddee, pending_org_::1e256cd067fcd22ea	multiple OpenAIRE IDs
Netherlands Institute for Neuroscience	NIN	KNAW	05csn2x06	I1295801184	openorgs_::b411400e9cb43b74991acf165fdbaf42	
Netherlands Institute of Ecology (NIOO)	NIOO	KNAW	01g25jp36	I4210107786	openorgs_::938a3404eacaedfe1b192d39178606eb, pending_org_::f07a375b45532443ece49d3a504d74f4	multiple OpenAIRE IDs
Netherlands Interdisciplinary Demographic Institute (NIDI)	NIDI	KNAW	04kf5kc54	I4210154073	openorgs_::30f7a1b7ffaca5405d4fc22b45b346f8	
NIOD Institute for War, Holocaust and Genocide studies	NIOD	KNAW	05he87q93	I175771706	openorgs_::64ff9bf918bf9552b30ba878bbf3eba6	
Royal Netherlands Institute of Southeast Asian and Caribbean Studies (KITLV)	KITLV	KNAW	01bdv4312	I39431069	openorgs_::6a6ff788c9f916d156e88942155543c8	
Westerdijk Fungal Biodiversity Institute	WESTERDIJK	KNAW	030a5r161	I4210113371	openorgs_::e9afeb0f06cd2672f64eba5c50b58508	

RPO name	acronym	group	ROR ID	OpenAlex ID	OpenAIRE ID	notes
Aeres University of Applied Sciences	AERES	VH	01xpgs822	I2799589116	openorgs::43e6dc2e3207f47c82560767ed928bab	
Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences	HVA	VH	00y2z2s03	I55106644	openorgs::d0a66a264d47d18baba1821d678627f3, pending_org::c66e50e36cefdb59df4301d2b6533fec	multiple OpenAIRE IDs
Amsterdam University/School of the Arts	AHK	VH	04dde1554	I4210135670	openorgs::57a751ebab17a6996ba6836a89548f35	
ArtEZ University of the Arts	ARTEZ	VH	05az93f25	I2800460346	openorgs::e79c2bf184a99250523a378626875955	
Avans University of Applied Sciences	AVANS	VH	015d5s513	I151001089	openorgs::05ba90eee0e9eef094a77240339d0ee5	
Christian University of Applied Sciences Viaa	CHE	VH	04tj5wz42	I30702933	openorgs::04a66697fcec5d5e3bbf19b85135356	
Codarts, University for the Arts	CODARTS	VH	04vtvrr13	I2801429410	openorgs::bb88336ade9d2deeece4de6262054b4	
De Kempel University of Applied Sciences	KEMPEL	VH	056k6yz11	I4210155229	openorgs::4aebd7bd67813bb8a325eb410a392be	
Design Academy Eindhoven	DESIGN	VH	039vq9023	I68976167	openorgs::4b2a9d306955ede352ba267af8616375	

RPO name	acronym	group	ROR ID	OpenAlex ID	OpenAIRE ID	notes
Driestar Christian University for Teacher Education	DRIESTAR	VH	05jext738	I4210164431	openorgs::2d77f3a9829f7a9651ec60f597b479cd	
Fontys University of Applied Sciences	FONTYS	VH	01jwcme05	I21516984	openorgs::2885352ab1a441a9d387424888e30796	
Gerrit Rietveld Academie	RIETVELD	VH	053jpid80	I2800065634	openorgs::95e5f0e3696306902a6749c406bb2728	
HAN University of Applied Sciences	HAN	VH	0500gea42	I103855431	openorgs::048a44d990fd8a4710eef3a9e375360b	
Hanze University of Applied Sciences Groningen	HANZE	VH	00xqtxw43	I180755707	openorgs::c254f2d5f6fdb12ecb37cfee25a3c4b1	
HAS Green Academy	HAS GREEN	VH	05p706d77	I4210166725	openorgs::775eab3c1281cb91d53a31c4a1ba1090	
Hotelschool The Hague	HOTELSCHOOL	VH	018t8yw14	I2800143506	openorgs::a5ac6dbe326433376c900329853d914a	
HZ University of Applied Sciences	HZ	VH	047cqa323	I21019838	openorgs::de44646096a724bdba876f7f573e74eb	
Inholland University of Applied Sciences	INHOLLAND	VH	03cfsyg37	I896005021	openorgs::5f081781d2510771c1c6686c4a37d1a1	
IPABO, University of Professional Teacher Education	IPABO	VH	0230zs006	I4210110308	openorgs::3f27054a1ab469826b9d3a1915452f89	

RPO name	acronym	group	ROR ID	OpenAlex ID	OpenAIRE ID	notes
Iselinge University of Professional Teacher Education	ISELINGE	VH	047kqmy39	I4210154467	openorgs::74691942ddde3989519f008b551ebb35	
Katholieke (Catholic) Pabo Zwolle, KPZ	KPZ	VH	05nrjb178	I4210164235	openorgs::0ac7645722cfee8253ce68cd2ab609c6	
Marnix Academie University for Teacher education	MARNIX	VH	03xws5b35	I4210139697	openorgs::8cf49add8601037458e4ecdbd63a1c42	
NHL Stenden University of Applied Sciences	STENDEN	VH	02xgxme97 (current), 026xbkx09 (previous)	I36523846 , I4387154156	openorgs::7ef128431ed7a002d362e73a048d3fd5 , pending_org::722d6fee5ef1663527379a9e837bffb1	multiple OpenAlex and OpenAIRE IDs, linked to previous and current ROR
NHTV Breda University of Applied Sciences	NHTV	VH	04mfj5474	I128589980	openorgs::10020843b2d7fac7c04e40b55a631b0c	
Rotterdam University of Applied Sciences	HR	VH	0481e1q24	I907135538	openorgs::7ec8de16e11c7fc9f7e4e32923a42b22	
Royal Academy of Art	KABK	VH	00490vc18	I4210088845	openorgs::919801f3040011bbef2dd28020917c7f	
Royal Conservatory The Hague	KC	VH	01mwwwn80	I3129625411	openorgs::58d238642a71a8cf41bd68c3e4189151	
Saxion University of Applied Sciences	SAXION	VH	005t9n460	I2801398864	openorgs::e086dd85625f9fe8b89dfc2d81441664	

RPO name	acronym	group	ROR ID	OpenAlex ID	OpenAIRE ID	notes
The Hague University of Applied Sciences	THUAS	VH	021zvq422	I930713850	openorgs::b232880c47fb92a22ffea8e2e749e0ac	
University of Applied Sciences Leiden	UAS LEIDEN	VH	0093src13	I210716285	openorgs::913ef94a4bc903f936164b00f287defa	
University of Applied Sciences Utrecht	HU	VH	028z9kw20	I173063890	openorgs::8a1b859747bd305bc855914588006010	
University of the Arts Utrecht: HKU	HKU	VH	018bzip792	I2802751956	openorgs::c143bad570ce1ce6c1c5956f5f2d96ee	
Van Hall Larenstein VHL University of Applied Sciences	VHL	VH	02mdbnd10	I2800435062	openorgs::06b2bdd4093a09b5f6c33521a7bf665c	
Windesheim University of Applied Sciences	WINDESHEIM	VH	04zmc0e16	I242486142	openorgs::a08a62c3e21dd693af009638e21aba11	
Zuyd University of Applied Sciences	ZUYD	VH	02m6k0m40	I193397943	openorgs::0e7e1aa241c64ac17aee64c0be4be069	
Thomas More Hogeschool	(not included)	VH	-	-	-	
Viaa University of Applied Sciences	(not included)	VH	-	-	-	

Appendix 2

Overlap OpenAlex-OpenAIRE (publication year 2022) - by RPO / RPO group

name	group	OpenAlex without DOI	OpenAlex with DOI	both - OpenAlex different year	OpenAlex and OpenAIRE	both - OpenAIRE different year	OpenAIRE with DOI	OpenAIRE without DOI
UNL/NFU	UNL/NFU	463	22505	1286	48245	1137	18635	25415
NWO-i	NWO-i	12	969	33	841	38	477	114
KNAW	KNAW	4	729	13	281	16	759	112
VH	VH	22	1358	16	907	17	250	76

name	group	OpenAlex without DOI	OpenAlex with DOI	both - OpenAlex different year	OpenAlex and OpenAIRE	both - OpenAIRE different year	OpenAIRE with DOI	OpenAIRE without DOI
EUR/ ErasmusMC	UNL/NFU	38	4759	95	2491	50	485	406
RU/ RadboudUMC	UNL/NFU	52	2576	160	5580	155	1994	3395
RUG/UMCG	UNL/NFU	38	3984	137	4723	94	2022	598
TiU	UNL/NFU	5	866	42	809	26	194	97
TUD	UNL/NFU	30	1162	142	5707	128	2296	1396
TUE	UNL/NFU	23	1525	39	2043	32	782	178
UL/LUMC	UNL/NFU	36	2768	100	5871	93	2817	3153
UM/ MaastrichtMC	UNL/NFU	42	1387	87	4948	86	2034	4755

UU/UMCU	UNL/NFU	79	4320	185	6238	141	2572	2762
UVA/AMC	UNL/NFU	32	4520	147	4336	100	2248	488
UVT	UNL/NFU	10	652	63	2574	59	1201	1330
VU/VUMC	UNL/NFU	62	1802	165	5050	181	5489	5414
WUR	UNL/NFU	19	719	108	4332	133	2156	2094
OU	UNL/NFU	1	138	8	355	14	183	771
AUMC	UNL/NFU	60	6302	27	1110	19	449	239

name	group	OpenAlex without DOI	OpenAlex with DOI	both - OpenAlex different year	OpenAlex and OpenAIRE	both - OpenAIRE different year	OpenAIRE with DOI	OpenAIRE without DOI
AMOLF	NWO-i	0	139	1	5	1	13	1
ARCNL	NWO-i	0	50	0	23	0	8	0
ASTRON	NWO-i	11	189	3	101	0	103	0
CWI	NWO-i	0	153	7	124	7	104	37
DIFFER	NWO-i	0	21	6	84	1	40	18
NIKHEF	NWO-i	0	163	0	12	0	15	1
NIOZ	NWO-i	1	142	5	299	18	60	45
NSCR	NWO-i	0	55	3	34	4	9	0
SRON	NWO-i	0	96	8	162	8	136	12

name	group	OpenAlex without DOI	OpenAlex with DOI	both - OpenAlex different year	OpenAlex and OpenAIRE	both - OpenAIRE different year	OpenAIRE with DOI	OpenAIRE without DOI
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HUBRECHT	KNAW	0	66	0	1	0	0	0
HUYGENS	KNAW	1	70	0	7	0	0	4
IISH	KNAW	1	90	0	8	0	3	4
KITLV	KNAW	0	11	3	5	0	1	1
MEERTENS	KNAW	0	10	0	5	0	1	0
NIDI	KNAW	0	46	1	20	0	0	3
NIN	KNAW	0	218	2	67	7	15	24
NIOD	KNAW	1	18	0	2	3	1	0
NIOO	KNAW	1	147	5	128	4	727	73
WESTERDIJK	KNAW	0	60	2	40	2	12	3

name	group	OpenAlex without DOI	OpenAlex with DOI	both - OpenAlex different year	OpenAlex and OpenAIRE	both - OpenAIRE different year	OpenAIRE with DOI	OpenAIRE without DOI
AERES	VH	0	3	0	0	0	1	0
AHK	VH	0	156	0	4	0	1	0
ARTEZ	VH	0	13	0	0	0	0	0
AVANS	VH	0	51	1	31	0	6	2
CHE	VH	0	8	0	12	0	2	0
CODARTS	VH	0	57	0	0	0	0	0
DESIGN	VH	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
DRIESTAR	VH	0	2	0	2	0	0	0
FONTYS	VH	1	78	0	64	0	3	2
HAN	VH	1	107	1	98	3	109	12

HANZE	VH	0	94	0	98	1	97	17
HAS GREEN	VH	0	0	0	0	0	48	1
HKU	VH	0	50	0	2	0	1	0
HOTELSCHOOL	VH	0	16	0	3	0	0	0
HR	VH	1	109	1	74	0	29	4
HU	VH	6	162	1	83	0	28	6
HVA	VH	9	162	3	129	5	28	30
HZ	VH	1	13	1	15	0	36	0
INHOLLAND	VH	0	24	2	42	1	20	2
IPABO	VH	1	3	0	1	0	0	0
ISELINGE	VH	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
KABK	VH	0	12	0	0	0	0	0
KC	VH	0	4	0	0	0	2	0
KEMPEL	VH	0	2	0	0	0	0	0
KPZ	VH	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
MARNIX	VH	0	4	0	1	0	0	0
NHTV	VH	0	38	2	31	1	2	0
RIETVELD	VH	0	1	0	2	0	0	0
SAXION	VH	0	47	1	29	0	9	6
STENDEN	VH	1	32	1	55	0	10	1
THUAS	VH	0	77	0	55	2	9	0
UAS LEIDEN	VH	0	32	2	20	1	18	2
VHL	VH	0	21	0	7	1	1	0
WINDESHEIM	VH	1	35	0	45	0	5	8

ZUYD	VH	0	44	0	63	4	16	0
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Appendix 3

Overlap OpenAlex-OpenAIRE (publication year 2022, DOIs only, UNL / NFU) - by Crossref type

Crossref type	OpenAlex with DOI	both - OpenAlex different year	OpenAlex and OpenAIRE	both - OpenAIRE different year	OpenAIRE with DOI
journal-article	16290	1101	41588	1015	5107
posted-content	1689	42	2374	47	707
book-chapter	2440	95	1136	3	561
proceedings-article	722	10	2638	12	358
dissertation	3	0	0	0	874
peer-review	346	0	77	1	96
dataset	235	0	85	0	0
book	58	2	14	0	83
other	87	2	20	0	29
monograph	40	1	17	0	44
report	7	0	9	2	11
edited-book	2	0	16	0	5
reference-entry	2	0	4	0	11

proceedings	2	0	0	0	0
journal-issue	1	0	0	0	0
null	581	33	267	57	10749